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Attitude of Indian University Students Towards Green Consumption Behaviour

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Abstract

Green consumer attitudes reflect the values that drive consumers to buy environmentally friendly products. Green consumer value can be explained as consumers' behavior toward products, which is affected by their green buying attitude. The present study was conducted in four Agricultural Universities of India and the sample comprised 336 students. A self-structured interview schedule was developed to study the attitude of the students towards green consumption behaviour. The study found that respondents had a favourable attitude (44.94%) followed closely by the most favourable attitude (42.55%) and a few had the least favourable attitude (12.5%). Gender comparison shows no significant gender difference. Caste ($\chi^2 = 0.128^*$), father's occupation ($\chi^2 = 0.147^{**}$) and mother's occupation ($\chi^2 = 0.123^*$) exhibited significant associations with respondents' attitude and family education showed a significant positive correlation with attitude ($r = 0.170$, $p < 0.01$). Attitude of the respondents towards green consumption behaviour was relatively similar across all universities, (93.91 ± 8.58 each in PAU and CAU), (94.01 ± 8.84 in MPUAT) and (95.11 ± 11.83 in PJTSAU) and the differences were statistically non-significant ($F = 0.30$, $p = 0.820$). Overall, the study demonstrates that agricultural university students in India largely possess favourable attitudes toward green consumption, reinforced by family education, socio-cultural factors, and institutional exposure.

Keywords: Attitude; Gender comparison; Correlation; Association

Introduction

Over the past few decades, rapid industrialization, urbanization, and unsustainable consumption patterns have led to severe environmental degradation. The overexploitation of natural resources, increasing waste generation, and the extensive use of non-biodegradable materials have posed serious threats to ecological balance and human well-being. In response to these challenges, the concept of green consumption has gained prominence as a sustainable approach to mitigate environmental harm. Green consumption emphasizes the purchase and use of products and services that cause minimal adverse effects on the environment and promote the conservation of natural resources. It encourages consumers to adopt a lifestyle that integrates environmental consciousness into everyday choices, thereby contributing to long-term sustainability.

Green consumption behaviour refers to the psychological and behavioural processes through which individuals make environmentally responsible decisions in their purchasing and consumption activities. It involves not only the act of buying eco-friendly products but also the conscious efforts to minimize waste, conserve resources, and support sustainable production systems. According to (Liobikiene and Bernatoniene, 2017), green consumer attitudes are largely influenced by internal values that motivate individuals to prefer eco-friendly goods, even when these products are slightly more expensive than conventional alternatives. Consumers today are becoming increasingly aware of the consequences of pollution and resource depletion, and many demonstrate a positive inclination toward green products. In recent years, cultural and societal pressures to choose environmentally responsible products have also intensified (Oliva et al., 2024). The theory of consumption values explains that consumers' preferences and decisions are influenced by a

combination of personal, social, psychological, and economic factors. These factors together shape how individuals perceive and respond to opportunities for green consumption. A positive attitude toward green consumption arises from values such as environmental concern, ethical responsibility, and social awareness. Such attitudes motivate individuals to adopt sustainable purchasing patterns and choose products that are less harmful to the environment (Haba et al., 2023). In recent years, consumers have become increasingly conscious of environmental issues and prefer brands that reflect sustainability, transparency, and responsibility. As a result, businesses across the world are focusing on developing and promoting eco-friendly goods and services, recognizing that consumer attitudes play a crucial role in the shift toward sustainability.

In modern society, consumers are showing a stronger inclination toward green consumerism and are often willing to spend more on environmentally friendly products. This behaviour reflects growing ecological awareness and the desire to contribute to environmental protection through responsible consumption choices. No doubt, the translation of a positive attitude into actual sustainable practices depends on adequate knowledge, awareness, and motivation. Sustainable consumption requires not only understanding but also active participation and integration of eco-friendly actions into everyday life. Building a deeply rooted positive attitude toward environmental responsibility is therefore essential to overcome these challenges (Warde, 2005).

Although many consumers express a favourable attitude toward green products, a gap often exists between intentions and actual behaviour. People may be influenced by social norms, convenience, or situational factors that prevent them from acting in accordance with their environmental values. Nevertheless, maintaining a positive attitude remains the foundation for behavioural change.

Education plays a vital role in shaping positive attitudes toward green consumption. Environmental learning enhances awareness, strengthens responsibility, and encourages individuals to make informed choices that support sustainability. People with greater environmental knowledge are generally more aware of the consequences of their consumption habits and are more likely to engage in environmentally responsible behaviour (Lin and Niu, 2018). Hence, improving environmental education can significantly contribute to the development of positive attitudes and sustainable consumption practices. When individuals internalize environmental values, their attitudes are more likely to manifest in consistent green purchasing behaviour, leading to long-term environmental preservation and sustainable development. Therefore, the present study was conducted to study the attitude of students towards green consumption behaviour.

Methodology

The present study was conducted across four Agricultural Universities in India, representing the southern, northern, eastern, and western regions of the country. From the southern region, Professor Jayashankar Telangana State Agricultural University (PJTSAU), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, was selected. Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, Punjab, represented the northern region, while the eastern region was represented by Central Agricultural University (CAU), Imphal, Manipur. Maharana Pratap University of Agriculture and Technology (MPUAT), Udaipur, Rajasthan, was chosen to represent the western region. A total of 84 students were selected from each university, including 28 undergraduate, 28 postgraduate (M.Sc.), and 28 doctoral (Ph.D.) students, irrespective of their specialization. Thus, the overall sample consisted of 336 students. To control extraneous variables, equal representation of male and female students was ensured across all universities. There were 22 statements related to attitude about green consumption behaviour. The responses to the statements regarding attitude of the respondents towards green consumption behaviour were collected using five-point Likert scale. Thus, the attitude score of the respondents was calculated using category interval methods, ranges for these levels of attitude were made i.e. least favourable, favourable and most favourable. Thereafter, respondents were categorised into three levels.

Result and discussion

Attitude of the respondents about green consumption behaviour

The data presented in Table 1 show the attitude mean scores of respondents from the selected universities towards green consumption behaviour on a 5-point continuum.

A glance at the table, depicts that majority of them were having favourable attitude towards green consumption behaviour as the mean for most of the statements was near four.

Respondents strongly agreed with statements such as valuing clean and green surroundings (mean = 4.63, rank 1), preference for environment friendly products (mean = 4.52, rank 2). They agreed for

irritation with open burning (mean = 4.49, rank 3), concern for changes in environment and feeling social responsibility to protect our environment (mean = 4.47, rank 4.5 each), irritation over throwing garbage out of the car (mean = 4.46, rank 6), willingness to participate in environmental programme (mean = 4.45, rank 7), appreciating items made from natural ingredients and willingness to change lifestyle to conserve environment (mean = 4.42, rank 8.5), care about environmental problems (mean = 4.37, rank 10.5) each, in that order. There was not much difference across universities for the attitude towards these statements. Further the respondents agreed on valuing clean road side (mean = 4.36, rank 12), feeling responsibility for keeping clean environment (mean = 4.34, rank 13), appreciating environment friendly products and favouring clothes made from linen, hemp or wool (mean = 4.32, rank 14.5) each, willingness to come by bicycle (mean = 4.25, rank 16), irritation due to pollution (mean = 4.24, rank 17), followed by conserving for solid waste disposal problems (mean = 4.04, rank 18), appreciating recycling campaigns (mean = 3.76, rank 19), preferring carry shopping bags (mean = 3.59, rank 20), priority to natural environment (mean = 3.52, rank 21). However, appreciating plantation drives (mean = 3.36, rank 22) were ranked comparatively low overall agreement for each statement was observed among all university students.

Table 1. Attitude of respondents from selected universities towards green consumption behaviour, N=336

Aspects	University				Overall	Rank
	PAU	MPUAT	CAU	PJTSAU		
Value clean and green surrounding	4.63	4.67	4.64	4.59	4.63	1
Prefer environment friendly products	4.51	4.59	4.53	4.47	4.52	2
Irritation with open burning	4.46	4.51	4.42	4.58	4.49	3
Feel social responsibility to protect our environment	4.40	4.55	4.41	4.52	4.47	4.5
Concerned for changes in environment	4.38	4.46	4.38	4.66	4.47	4.5
Irritation over throwing garbage out of the car	4.47	4.45	4.51	4.42	4.46	6
Willingness to participate in environmental programme	4.41	4.42	4.42	4.57	4.45	7
Appreciate items made from natural ingredients	4.46	4.40	4.47	4.36	4.42	8.5
Willingness to change lifestyle to conserve environment	4.29	4.35	4.29	4.78	4.42	8.5
Care about environmental problems	4.35	4.45	4.38	4.30	4.37	10.5
Consider before buying products	4.25	4.39	4.27	4.59	4.37	10.5
Value clean road side	4.51	4.23	4.35	4.35	4.36	12
Feel responsible for keeping clean environment	4.26	4.41	4.26	4.44	4.34	13
Appreciate environment friendly products	4.55	3.61	4.57	4.57	4.32	14.5
Favour clothes made from linen, hemp or wool	4.23	4.29	4.26	4.51	4.32	14.5
Willingness to come by bicycle	4.15	4.20	4.15	4.51	4.25	16
Irritation due to pollution	4.15	4.19	4.16	4.46	4.24	17
Concerned for solid waste disposal problems	4.33	4.38	4.34	4.14	4.04	18
Appreciate recycling campaigns	3.79	3.82	3.77	3.69	3.76	19
Prefer carry shopping bags	3.91	2.46	3.92	4.09	3.59	20
Prioritize natural environment	3.65	3.66	3.63	3.17	3.52	21
Appreciate plantation drives	3.83	3.57	2.47	3.60	3.36	22
Mean	4.27 ^a	4.18 ^a	4.20 ^a	4.33 ^a	4.43	

Score range: 1 (Strongly disagree) – 5 (Strongly agree)

Means followed by common letter represent non-significant difference

The results are aligned with the work conducted by (Kennedy et al., 2024) who found that young Indian consumers show a positive orientation toward sustainable lifestyles and green product usage, and by (Rivera et al., 2024) observed that environmental concern and pro-environmental identity significantly influence favourable attitudes toward green purchasing.

Statements expressing behavioural willingness, such as participating in environmental programme and willingness to change lifestyle to conserve the environment were highly rated, suggesting readiness among students to translate their concern into action. However, lower mean values were observed for statements involving more effortful or habitual changes such as appreciating recycling campaigns, preferring to carry shopping bags and appreciating plantation drives. The results are aligned with the study conducted by (Kirmani and Khan, 2021; Zhang et al., 2024) who recognised attitude-behaviour gap in green consumption. Strong attitudes toward environmental protection do not always manifest as consistent pro-environmental behaviour due to factors like convenience, perceived cost, or product availability.

Overall mean score of the attitude for each university was calculated and comparison shows that PJTSAU (mean=4.33) students had more favourable attitude towards green consumption behaviour followed by PAU (mean=4.27), CAU (mean=4.18), and MPUAT (mean=4.20) in that order. However, these was not statistically significant. The results are aligned with findings by (Zhao, 2021; Chaudhary and Bisai, 2022), who noted that university environments often minimize demographic

disparities in sustainability attitudes through exposure to similar curricula and environmental initiatives.

Attitude level of respondents towards green consumption behaviour

The data presented in Table 2 shows the level of attitude of respondents towards green consumption behaviour.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents across universities according to their level of attitude towards green consumption behaviour, N =336

Attitude	University				Overall f (%)
	PAU n ₁ =84 f (%)	MPUAT n ₂ =84 f (%)	CAU n ₃ =84 f (%)	PJTSAU n ₄ =84 f (%)	
Least favourable (69-82)	7 (8.33)	7(8.33)	7 (8.33)	21(25.00)	42 (12.5)
Favourable (83-96)	46 (54.76)	44(52.38)	45 (53.57)	16(19.04)	151(44.94)
Most favourable (97-110)	31 (36.90)	33(39.28)	32 (38.09)	47(55.95)	143 (42.55)

The table reveals that overall, a large proportion of the respondents had favourable attitude (44.94%) followed closely by most favourable attitude (42.55%), though few had least favourable attitude (12.5%). Almost similar pattern was seen in all the universities i.e. among the university, majority of the respondents from PAU (54.76%) followed by CAU (53.57%), MPUAT (52.38%) while only (19.04%) PJTSAU had favourable attitude. This was because majority of PJTSAU students were in most favourable attitude category (55.95%). This was followed by MPUAT (39.28%), CAU (38.09%) and PAU (36.90%). Interestingly, in least favourable attitude, majority of the respondents were from PJTSAU (25.00%) followed by PAU, MPUAT and CAU (8.33% each). The findings are aligned with work conducted by (Kennedy et al., 2024; Chaudhary and Bisai, 2022), who reported that young consumers, particularly university students, exhibit highly favourable attitudes toward eco-friendly products and sustainable living due to increased environmental awareness and exposure to sustainability education.

Gender comparison for attitude about green consumption behaviour

The data in the table 3 compares male and female respondents for their level of attitude towards green consumption behaviour.

Table 3. Gender comparison across universities among respondents for their attitude towards green consumption behaviour, N=336

Attitude	University								Overall	
	PAU		MPUAT		CAU		PJTSAU		M n _i =168 f (%)	F n _j =168 f (%)
	M n _a =42 f (%)	F n _b =42 f (%)	M n _c =42 f (%)	F n _d =42 f (%)	M n _e =42 f (%)	F n _f =42 f (%)	M n _g =42 f (%)	F n _h =42 f (%)		
Least favourable (69-82)	2 (4.76)	5 (11.90)	1 (2.38)	6 (14.28)	2 (4.76)	5 (11.90)	11 (26.19)	10 (23.80)	16 (9.52)	26 (15.47)
Favourable (83-96)	27 (64.28)	19 (45.23)	25 (59.52)	19 (45.23)	27 (64.28)	18 (42.85)	7 (16.66)	9 (21.42)	86 (51.19)	65 (38.69)
Most favourable (97-110)	13 (30.95)	18 (42.85)	16 (38.09)	17 (40.47)	13 (30.95)	19 (45.23)	24 (57.14)	23 (54.76)	66 (39.28)	77 (45.83)
Mean±SD	93.14 ±8.40	94.69 ±8.79	93.69 ±7.22	94.33 ±10.28	93.14 ±8.40	94.83 ±8.57	95.61 ±12.11	94.61 ±11.65	93.89 ±9.19	94.61 ±9.82
Mann Whitney U test (Z value)	1.075 ^{NS}		0.627 ^{NS}		1.291 ^{NS}		0.660 ^{NS}		1.022 ^{NS}	

NS = non-significant

The overall findings indicate that there were more male (51.19%) in favourable category while in most favourable category more female respondents were observed, whereas a smaller proportion of respondents demonstrated least favourable attitude.

In PAU, around two-thirds of male respondents (64.28%) compared to the lesser female respondents (45.23%) had favourable attitude while more female respondents (42.85%) as compared to female respondents (30.95%) had the most favourable attitude. Female respondents (11.90%) were higher than male respondents (4.76%) in least favourable attitude category. The difference in male and female respondents' attitude was non-significant when Mann Whitney U test was applied. If we compare the overall mean for male and female respondents at PAU, female respondents (94.69±8.79) had slightly higher mean score than male respondents (93.14±8.40).

In MPUAT, majority of male respondents (59.52%) compared to lesser female respondents (45.23%) expressed a favourable attitude, while female respondents (40.47%) were more than the male respondents (38.09%) in the most favourable category. Female respondents (14.28%) were higher than male respondents (2.38%) in least favourable attitude category. The gender difference was however non-significant. Overall, in MPUAT, the attitude of the female respondents (94.33 ± 10.28) was higher than male respondents (93.69 ± 7.22).

In CAU, 64.28 per cent of male respondents demonstrated a favourable attitude, compared to 42.85% of female respondents. More female respondents showed most favourable attitude (45.23%) compared to male respondents (30.95%). Similarly female respondents (11.90%) were more than male respondent (4.76%) in least favourable attitude category. Here also gender difference was non-significant. In CAU, the mean score shows that the female respondents (94.83 ± 8.57) were reported marginally higher score than male respondents (93.14 ± 8.40).

PJTSAU was found to have a larger proportion of male respondents (57.14%) as well as female respondents (54.76%) with the most favourable attitude while about one fourth (21.42%) female respondents reported a favourable attitude compared to lesser male respondents (16.66%). Further, about one-fourth of male respondents (26.19%) and nearly the same proportion of females (23.80%) were in the least favourable category. The difference in male and female respondents was non-significant. In PJTSAU, male recorded higher mean score (95.61 ± 12.11) than female (94.61 ± 11.65).

So, overall, it can be observed that more male respondents (51.19%) had favourable attitude as compared to female respondents (38.69%), whereas more female respondents 45.83% had most favourable attitude as compared to male (39.28%). In the least favourable category, comparatively smaller, female respondents (15.47%) were seen higher than male respondents (9.52%). The difference was however not significant. The data reveal that the overall attitude mean score of female respondents (94.61 ± 9.82) was slightly higher than male respondents (93.89 ± 9.19).

These results are aligned with work by (Lee, 2009) reported that there were no significant gender differences in adolescent consumers' green attitudes, suggesting a convergence of environmental concern across genders. Further (Kumar and Mohanty, 2022) reported that among university students, gender disparities in environment attitudes tend to narrow. This is often attributed to equal exposure to sustainability-related education, environmental campaigns, digital awareness that transcend boundaries.

Correlation of socio-personal profile of respondents with knowledge, attitude and practices about green consumption behaviour

Table 4 presents the correlation between selected socio-personal characteristics and respondents' attitudes toward green consumption behaviour.

Table 4. Correlation of socio personal profile with attitude of respondents towards green consumption behaviour, N=336

Socio personal profile	Attitude
Education	0.024 ^{NS}
Family size	0.002 ^{NS}
Family income	0.039 ^{NS}
Family Education	0.170**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level, NS = non-significant

Among all variables, family education showed a significant positive correlation with attitude ($r = 0.170$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that respondents whose family members possessed higher educational qualifications tends to hold more positive attitudes toward green consumption. However, the data reveal that self-education ($r = 0.024^{\text{NS}}$), family size ($r = 0.002^{\text{NS}}$), and family income ($r = 0.039^{\text{NS}}$) were not significantly correlated with attitude.

The results are aligned with findings by (Rivera et al., 2024) emphasized that family educational background contributes to forming stronger moral and cognitive orientations toward environmental sustainability. (Zhao, 2021 and Zhang et al., 2024) reported that within university, students' exposure to sustainability of the environment tends to be relatively uniform. Similarly, (Kirmani and Khan, 2021) who observed that education improves attitudes and behaviours of the students which strongly shaped by personal values and perceived behavioural control. The correlation between family size and attitude indicates that number does not substantially influence

individual environmental orientations. However, study conducted by (Kennedy et al., 2024) who highlighted that higher income enhances the ability to purchase eco-friendly products but not their attitude.

Association of socio personal profile with attitude about green consumption behaviour

Table 5 presents the association between socio-personal profile and attitude of the respondents toward green consumption behaviour.

Table 5. Association of socio personal profile with attitude about green consumption behaviour, N=336

Socio personal profile	Attitude
Age	0.016 ^{NS}
Gender	0.038 ^{NS}
Residence	0.013 ^{NS}
Caste	0.128*
Family background	0.089 ^{NS}
Family type	0.045 ^{NS}
Father's occupation	0.147**
Mother's occupation	0.123*

** Significant difference at the 0.01 level, * Significant difference at 0.05 level, NS = non-significant

The data reveal that age ($\chi^2 = 0.016^{NS}$), gender ($\chi^2 = 0.038^{NS}$), residence ($\chi^2 = 0.013^{NS}$), family background ($\chi^2 = 0.089^{NS}$) and family type ($\chi^2 = 0.045^{NS}$), did not show significant association with attitude whereas caste ($\chi^2 = 0.128^*$), father's occupation ($\chi^2 = 0.147^{**}$) and mother's occupation ($\chi^2 = 0.123^*$) exhibited significant association with respondents' attitudes toward green consumption, suggesting that parental occupational status may influence the development of pro-environmental attitudes.

The results are aligned with study conducted by (Jaiswal and Kant, 2024) which reported that parents working in environmentally aware professions (e.g., education or health) often transmit pro-sustainability attitudes through daily conversations, lifestyle modelling, and consumption choices.

Comparison of respondents across universities according to attitude about green consumption behaviour

The data presented in Table 6 compares the respondents across the four selected universities with respect to their attitude towards green consumption behaviour.

Table 6. Comparison of respondents across universities according to attitude about green consumption behaviour, N=336

Levels	University				f value	p value
	PAU n ₁ =84	MPUAT n ₂ =84	CAU n ₃ =84	PJTSAU n ₄ =84		
Attitude	93.91±8.58	94.01±8.84	93.98±8.48	95.11±11.83	0.30 ^{NS}	0.820

NS= non-significant

The data reveal that, the mean scores of the attitude of the respondents were relatively similar across all universities, (93.91 ± 8.58 each in PAU and CAU), (94.01±8.84 in MPUAT) and (95.11 ± 11.83 in PJTSAU). The differences were statistically non-significant (F = 0.30, p = 0.820), implying that respondents across universities held almost equally favourable attitudes towards green consumption behaviour. The presents findings are aligned with (Rivera et al., 2024), who noted that environmental attitudes among university students are shaped more by environmental consciousness and peer influence. Students, particularly those in agricultural and environmental disciplines, are increasingly aware of the need for responsible consumption and sustainable lifestyles, leading to consistent attitudinal patterns across universities.

Conclusion

The present study explored the attitude of college students towards green consumption behaviour across four Agricultural Universities in India. Overall, the findings indicate that a substantial proportion of students exhibited favourable or most favourable attitudes toward green consumption, reflecting a strong inclination toward environmentally responsible behaviours. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that agricultural university students in India largely possess favourable attitudes toward green consumption, reinforced by family education, socio-cultural

factors, and institutional exposure. While students show readiness to engage in environmentally friendly practices, the gap between attitude and actual behavioural adoption indicates the need for targeted interventions, such as promoting habitual green behaviours, enhancing practical environmental education, and facilitating accessible sustainable alternatives. Strengthening such initiatives can further nurture eco-conscious mindsets and translate favourable attitudes into consistent pro-environmental actions, contributing to sustainable consumption and environmental protection.

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Author Contributions

HB and RG conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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